

PERSONALITY TRAITS AND ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES OF THE TLE TEACHERS: THE MODERATING INFLUENCE OF SOCIOEMOTIONAL NEEDS

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Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Competencies of the TLE Teachers: The Moderating Influence of Socioemotional Needs

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Abstract

Entrepreneurial skills are key to economic growth, with teachers helping to incorporate them into lessons, while entrepreneurs must leverage their socioemotional skills to connect with customers, develop marketing strategies, and create a clear purpose and values for their businesses. This study determined the moderating influence of socioemotional needs on the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies among the 300 stratified randomly sampled T.L.E public secondary school teachers in the three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines using a non-experimental, quantitative, descriptive-correlational research design. The research instruments used were in the form of a standardized questionnaire, modified and contextualized to fit based on the research objectives. In analyzing the data, weighted mean, Pearson r , and Sobel's test were utilized. Findings revealed that there are high Level of Personality Traits, Entrepreneurial Competencies, and Socio Emotional Need. There exists a significant relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurship between personality traits and socio emotional needs and between socio emotional needs and entrepreneurship competencies of TLE Teachers existed. Utilizing Zobel's test, the results of the study revealed that there is a partial moderation among variables. This indicates that socioemotional needs do influence the relationship but do not fully explain the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies. Teachers with strong personality traits may have entrepreneurial skills; nevertheless, their performance might be influenced positively or negatively by their socioemotional needs.

Keywords: *Technology and Livelihood Education, moderation influence, socioemotional needs, personality traits, entrepreneurial competencies, Philippines*

Introduction

Entrepreneurial competencies are crucial catalysts for economic growth, with educators largely accountable for its incorporation into curricula and the identification of the most effective methodologies. Asian and other developing countries such as the Philippines are significantly promoting the concept on the importance of entrepreneurship as a priority that extensively contributes and enhances economic development and job creation (Huang et al., 2020). However, given many mediating circumstances, the principal policy inquiry persists about how to enhance entrepreneurial engagement and competencies among diverse persons, particularly concerning educators who are often left out. The increasing involvement of individuals in teaching and education has led to a lack of coordination and effective implementation between the labor market and the education system, resulting in many teachers failing to acquire essential abilities or relevant competencies (Chaker & Jarraya, 2021; Tu & Akhter, 2023).

Consequently, contemporary societal developments are both swift and complex, presenting considerable difficulties and new obligations to the educational sector. One particular response to the demand for such change is the recent emphasis on key competencies (Listiningrum et al., 2020; Miço & Cungu, 2023). Entrepreneurial competencies, characterized by initiative, creativity, risk-taking, and the capacity to transform ideas into action, are increasingly recognized as essential skills for each individual (Iqbal et al., 2022). It additionally corresponds to educators who, as advocates of entrepreneurial mindsets and behaviors across all educational levels, are compelled to adopt a more entrepreneurial attitude and practices. More so, a substantive discourse on teachers' entrepreneurial competencies is associated with the need to advance entrepreneurship education throughout all educational tiers (Lackéus, 2020). It is suggested that the quality of education needs to be improved by adopting innovative and creative teaching methods (Iwu et al., 2021) that are very beneficial in the current educational system in the Philippines.

Seemingly, teachers have a crucial role in transforming the multifaceted ideas of what entrepreneurship and being entrepreneurial means in the school context into teaching practices that will in the long run increase students' entrepreneurial competencies (Asikainen & Tapani, 2021). With the factors affecting entrepreneurial competencies, personality traits significantly influence competencies and intentions since they pertain to the enduring and stable psychological characteristics people possess (Friedman, 2020; Abid et al., 2021; Ciecuch & Strus, 2021). Further, socioemotional skills such as empathy, resilience, self-discipline, and confidence are personality traits that can be acquired through learning. Nonetheless, entrepreneurs must use their socioemotional skills to connect successfully with clients (Ali & Nadeem, 2021), develop marketing tactics (Paulynice, 2020), and construct a core goal and value system for their businesses (Huezo-Ponce et al., 2021).

The connection between personality traits and the entrepreneurial skills of teachers is rooted in the impact of intrinsic personal qualities on the skills and behaviors essential for entrepreneurial success. Teachers, particularly in disciplines such as Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), require entrepreneurial abilities to cultivate creativity, innovation, and practical application of knowledge. It fosters

innovation and adaptability, essential for learning about entrepreneurship, facilitates efficient time and resource management in classroom and project environments, promotes the exploration of novel teaching methodologies and business concepts, inspires and motivates students to participate in entrepreneurial endeavors, and aids in establishing trust and partnerships. In addition, extroverted teachers may actively want to belong and acknowledgment (Dronia, 2023) while conscientious teachers may prioritize autonomy and organization in their positions (Huang et al., 2023). In contrast, unfulfilled socioemotional demands may exacerbate negative characteristics (Serrano et al., 2023). Empirical evidence highlighting potential moderating influence of emotions, such as fear of failure among entrepreneurs existed (Stroe et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2020; Anjum et al., 2021; Younis et al., 2021).

The convergence of socioemotional needs, personality traits, and entrepreneurial competencies within the teaching profession, particularly among TLE teachers, is an inadequately studied domain. Although these categories have been examined individually to a degree, their collective impact and interaction in developing entrepreneurial abilities remain inadequately understood. Although studies has been done on socioemotional needs and entrepreneurial skills or personality traits and entrepreneurial abilities, few studies examine the dynamic interplay of these three components. Understanding of how socioemotional needs like as recognition and belonging influence the relationship between personality traits like openness and conscientiousness and the development of entrepreneurial competence is weak (Gabriela et al., 2021). Most studies emphasize generic teacher competencies, neglecting discipline-specific situations such as TLE, where entrepreneurial skills are crucial for teaching technical and livelihood-oriented subjects (Detmer Latorre, 2020). Teachers of TLE have distinct hurdles in incorporating entrepreneurship into the curriculum, requiring both emotional and certain personality traits.

Correspondingly, presented in Figure 1 the conceptual framework of the study includes the independent variable: personality traits by John et al., (1999) with the following indicators such as extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness; the dependent variable: entrepreneurial competencies which include indicators of conceptual, human relations, technical, commitment, opportunity, organizational, and strategic competencies as presented by Li (2009); and the moderating variable: socioemotional needs with indicators of initial training, coping with students' deficits, school/teacher needs, and learning/teaching process as presented by Moreira et al. (2013).

Figure 1. *The conceptual framework of the study*

Personality traits significantly shape the entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers, affecting how they teach, mentor, and prepare students for business. The Big Five traits influence communication, innovation, and management in entrepreneurship education (Bazkiaei et al., 2020). Extraversion enhances confidence, leadership, and networking (Mehta, 2024; Tauseef et al., 2024), while agreeableness fosters ethical business practices and teamwork (Kumari et al., 2022; Subramani et al., 2024). Conscientiousness supports organization, financial literacy, and strategic thinking (Matic et al., 2022), whereas well-managed neuroticism helps develop resilience and emotional intelligence (Wabule, 2020; Vega-Gómez et al., 2020; Volery & Mattes, 2022). Openness to experience drives creativity and adaptability, enabling teachers to integrate modern trends and technology (Kraus et al., 2021). Together, these traits help TLE teachers equip students with essential entrepreneurial skills for business success.

In personality traits, TLE teachers require technical competencies, including mastery of subject-specific knowledge, as well as entrepreneurial skills that foster creativity, innovation, and risk-taking among students. Teaching effectiveness include pedagogical abilities, classroom management, and curriculum delivery. Adaptability, including flexibility to manage developing pedagogical approaches and trends. Leadership and mentorship include directing students in initiatives and entrepreneurial activities (Bergner, 2020). It tailors training to utilize specific characteristics, employ personality assessments to identify teachers possessing traits

favorable for effective TLE instruction, offer socioemotional support to alleviate challenges associated with certain traits, and harness personality-driven strengths to create activities that promote entrepreneurial thinking in students (Liu et al., 2021).

This study is anchored on David McClelland's (1973 as cited by Wong, 2022 and Epikhin et al., 2023) Competency Theory, which asserts that competency is a complex and multifaceted construct including both general and specialized aspects. This construct is derived from observable behaviors and performance and is then extended to include underlying attributes. Barcelona et al., (2023) and Casas (2024) highlighted that enhancing the professional competency of TLE teachers and fostering a positive attitude towards classroom learning may result in an increased overall participation rate in the classroom. More so, extant literature presents two distinct conceptualizations of competency, trait theory (Fleeson & Jayawickreme, 2015) and behavior theory (Ajzen & Driver, 1991; Beck & Ajzen, 1991). Trait theory posits that the explanatory component of characteristics includes social-cognitive processes, indicating that the mechanisms responsible for producing Big-5 states should be delineated. This also rests on the idea of social-emotional learning, which is a way to get the self-awareness, self-control, and social skills required to do well in school, work, and life in general. In this study. This applies to how entrepreneurs develop self-control, self-preservation, relationship-building, and decision-making skills needed to deal with the different types of people one might interact with.

Consequently, entrepreneurial competencies which include indicators of conceptual, human relations, technical, commitment, opportunity, organizational, and strategic competencies, can establish feedback loops that motivate TLE teachers to cultivate or highlight certain personality qualities. This is particularly applicable in dynamic contexts where skills need adaptation, resilience, and proactive conduct (Henriksen et al., 2021). Consistent involvement in novel pedagogical techniques or entrepreneurial initiatives might augment teacher creativity and openness to new concepts (Keyhani & Kim, 2021).

Similarly, effectively integrating innovative business models into classes may encourage teachers to explore unconventional methods. The need for thorough planning, resource management, and goal setting in entrepreneurial activities might enhance conscientious behavior. Overseeing a student-led business initiative may compel a teacher to adopt more attention to detail and discipline (Chan, 2022). Mastery in entrepreneurial difficulties may alleviate anxiety and enhance mental stability, promoting resilience. Effectively managing losses in entrepreneurial pursuits might assist teachers in cultivating a more balanced emotional perspective (Ibrahim et al., 2022). Teachers develop competencies via practical entrepreneurial activities, necessitating the adaptation of their inherent qualities to address obstacles proficiently.

In addition, fulfilment of socioemotional needs, including belongingness, recognition, emotional support, and autonomy, promotes motivation, resilience, and creativity, hence intensifying the manifestation of personality traits and their influence on entrepreneurial competencies. Offering emotional and professional support may augment one's entrepreneurial skills by activating personality traits (Aly et al., 2021). Socioemotional needs serve as internal motivators that shape how personality traits are expressed and can enhance or hinder the development of entrepreneurial competencies.

Teachers who get robust emotional support and acknowledgment exhibit heightened motivation and engagement (Sadoughi & Hejazi, 2021). They are expected to use new methodologies and provide superior educational quality. Assists teachers in successfully incorporating authentic entrepreneurship situations into their lessons while A deficiency of acknowledgment or assistance may result in disengagement, diminishing efficacy in the delivery of TLE information. It may impede skill development owing to diminished morale or insufficient confidence (Karimi & Fallah, 2021). A conducive setting assists TLE teachers in navigating the intricacies of entrepreneurial and technical curricula. Emotional support sustains teacher motivation despite resource constraints (Tvedt et al., 2021).

There is a lack of longitudinal study examining the impact of socioemotional satisfaction and personality traits on entrepreneurial skills over time. The enduring consequences of unaddressed socioemotional demands on entrepreneurial competencies and personality development in teachers are inadequately recorded. Limited study examines the impact of socioemotional needs and personality traits on the entrepreneurial skills of teachers across various cultural or geographical settings (Moreira-Choez et al., 2024). In resource-limited educational institutions or collectivist societies, the interplay of socioemotional needs and their impact on entrepreneurial conduct may vary considerably. Studies on effective treatments or policy frameworks that promote teachers' socioemotional well-being to improve entrepreneurial competencies is scarce. The contemporary educational framework increasingly prioritizes entrepreneurship education to equip students for practical difficulties (Camacho Ortiz, 2020). Teachers, particularly in TLE, must possess entrepreneurial competencies to execute this efficiently. Socioemotional and personality traits are essential for facilitating this transition. The scant study on the entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers must be addressed. The researcher too, has no known local studies conducted focusing on the moderating effect of socioemotional needs on the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers. It is within this premise that this study was pursued

The study seeks to determine the moderating effect of socioemotional needs on the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers. Specifically, it sought to: (1) determine the level of personality traits in terms of extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness; (2) ascertain the entrepreneurial competencies in terms of conceptual competence, human relations competence, technical competence, commitment competence, opportunity competence, organizational competence and strategic competence; (3) measure the level of socioemotional needs; (4) establish the significance of the relationship between the personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies; between personality traits and socioemotional needs; between socioemotional needs and entrepreneurial competencies; and (5) determine moderating effect of socioemotional needs on the

relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies.

More so, the study hypothesized that socioemotional needs have no moderating effect on personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers. The assumption likely stems from existing psychological and entrepreneurship theories, which emphasize that personality traits are stable over time and have a direct impact on competencies. Since socioemotional needs can fluctuate due to external circumstances such as work environment, social relationships, or personal well-being, they may not have a strong or consistent influence on the way personality traits shape entrepreneurial competencies. The hypothesis assumes that socioemotional needs do not impact how personality traits influence entrepreneurial competencies, suggesting that personality alone is the primary factor shaping entrepreneurial skills in TLE teachers. However, further studies and empirical evidence are needed to confirm or challenge this assumption.

On the other hand, results of the study were seen to be global significant since entrepreneurship goes beyond local borders and shows how creativity, goods, and services can connect people all over the world. This speeds up economic growth and brings people from different cultures together, creating a global network of businesses and ideas. It is in the best interest of all enterprises to have the most important business skills, and this can be shared by teachers to students in improving competencies to be learned at school. These are the set of traits, attitudes, and actions that people have that allow them to spot chances, proceed with caution, and create a profitable business. The socioemotional needs, personality traits, and entrepreneurial skills of TLE teachers are essential for achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG #4) which aims for inclusive, equitable, and quality education. These factors help teachers provide high-quality education, promoting both academic and life skills in students. They ensure teachers are motivated, effective, and adaptable, fostering a supportive learning environment and integrating new technologies. By enhancing these qualities, TLE teachers can better prepare students for successful careers and contribute to meeting SDG #4's targets. This approach benefits education systems, workforce development, and social progress, while improving teacher satisfaction.

In similar ways, the key to being a successful teacher, especially for TLE teachers, is to have an interesting attitude or personality traits and business sense or entrepreneurial competencies. In addition to finding out what topics students are interested in, it helps teachers connect with them, come up with new ways to teach them, and make sure they fully grasp what they are being taught. The way people think, feel, and act in predictable ways are shown by their personality traits. Consistency and stability are what personality traits mean. For example, someone who scores high on the trait Extraversion is likely to be friendly in a variety of settings and over time. Knowing this may foster economic significance on how to deal people with varied personality traits, entrepreneurial competencies and socioemotional needs. Teachers whose socioemotional needs are satisfied and whose personality characteristics correspond with entrepreneurial skills are more adept at motivating students and fostering innovation in pedagogy.

Furthermore, the study was seen to benefit specific individuals like the school administrators, teachers, students and future researchers. For school administrators, it may provide better insights and information on the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers, evaluate the impact of socioemotional needs. This may aid a scientific framework for planning and executing interventions that could address issues or challenges to improve the TLE teachers' effectiveness and efficiency in serving diverse learners. For teachers and students, it may aid in disseminating awareness and foster deeper knowledge on entrepreneurial competencies and personality traits, and the moderating effect of socioemotional needs. For future researchers, it may serve as a reference when they will be conducting study of similar nature, adding to the existing knowledge and literature.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a non-experimental, quantitative, descriptive-correlational research design since it determined the moderating effect of socioemotional needs on the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers. Quantitative research employed objective measurement to gather numerical data used to answer research questions (Creswell, 2021). It is a deductive study in which the researcher inferred the characteristics of the investigated population based on the administered tests and surveys (Rassel et al., 2020). Consequently, it employed a descriptive-correlational design where it attempted to describe, evaluate, and discover the relationships between variables (Pandey & Pandey, 2021). It was used in the inquiry to analyze the existing condition of the phenomenon, which may be depicted as being in the form of variables (Szucs & Ioannidis, 2020; Kumatongo & Muzata, 2021; Taherdoost, 2022).

More so, mediation was used at it help to explain how or why a particular effect occurs (Nguyen et al., 2021). In the context of the study on personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers, with the moderating influence of socioemotional needs, mediation could be a fitting framework since it aimed to explore how socioemotional needs (as a mediator) help explain or influence the relationship between the teachers' personality traits (independent variable) and their entrepreneurial competencies (dependent variable). The reason mediation fits well in the study was that socioemotional needs could be the mechanism that explains how certain personality traits affect a teacher's ability to exhibit entrepreneurial competencies. For instance, a teacher with high openness may have a stronger entrepreneurial mindset, but socioemotional needs such as support or emotional regulation could mediate the relationship by affecting how the teacher develops and applies those competencies in the classroom (Mornar, 2024). Mediation focused on understanding the process that occurs (Hofmann et al., 2020) between the personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies, rather

than just identifying direct correlations. It helped in understanding the underlying processes by which socioemotional needs may influence the way personality traits impact entrepreneurial competencies.

Respondents

Respondents of the study were the 300 selected Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) public secondary school teachers in the three (3) districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines out of 3,249 public school teachers in a 206 Public Schools (Aquino, 2020) The selection of the respondents was done using stratified random where a population is divided into distinct subgroups or strata based on a shared characteristic such as belonging to different districts.

Once the population is divided into these strata, a random sample was taken from each subgroup (Iliyasu & Etikan, 2021). This would ensure that every subgroup was well-represented in the sample, which could lead to more accurate and reliable results (Howell et al., 2020). A population of 300 was assumed to be enough number of respondents (Ullah et al., 2022).

More so, 300 selected respondents were based on the recommendation that a larger size enhances statistical power and generalizability of quantitative surveys (McEwan, 2020; Althubaiti, 2023). The goal was to provide an outcome that can quantify both the significance of the investigation and the smallest discernible influence sizes (Lakens, 2022). Three hundred (300) respondents in a survey may be deemed enough in several instances, depending upon the research objectives, population size, and the requisite degree of statistical accuracy (Khakifirooz et al., 2021).

Correspondingly, it guaranteed dependable statistical inference (DeWees et al., 2020). Creswell (2021) suggested that a population of 300 subjected for study was large enough to provide statistical reliability and for significant generalizations on the population. It ensured that the study can handle complex statistical analyze and have sufficient statistical power to detect moderate to large effects. For a 95% level of significance and a 5% margin of error, 300 was often sufficient for populations of several thousand (Ahmed, 2024). Increasing population sizes needed progressively smaller increments in sample size to maintain an equivalent margin of error. It often reconciled practicality with the attainment of statistically valid outcomes (Gyllstad et al., 2021).

Furthermore so, Davao Occidental was selected as the place where the study since it was more accessible and convenient to the researcher, and this would make data gathering more expedient. Davao Occidental is a Philippine province located in the Davao Region of Mindanao and shares a maritime frontier with Indonesia's North Sulawesi province to the south. The province is bordered by Davao del Sur to the northwest, Sarangani to the west, and Davao Gulf to the northeast (Gula, 2022). Davao Occidental has a hilly, rocky, and sloping topography; mountains cover almost the whole province (Laugrand, 2022).

To yield trustworthy and reliable results, only qualified respondents and bona fide TLE teachers who were currently teaching within the three districts (Sta. Maria West, Sta. Maria East and Malita North Districts) of school division of Davao Occidental, had at least three years of teaching experience in the classroom for Junior and Senior High School regardless of teaching position, and employed in selected public secondary schools were qualified to be respondents of the study. Respondents must be within the given age range from 25-60 years old. In contrast, excluded were TLE teachers from private institutions. Respondents were given freedom to withdraw at any stage of the research process, at any time, for whatever reason they choose, and were not coerced, forced, or intimidated. The participation of the respondents must be done voluntarily, willfully and knowingly.

Instrument

The research instruments used in the study were in the form of a standardized questionnaire, modified and contextualized to fit based on the research objectives. since the study utilized a standardized questionnaire, it was adapted from various studies: John et al., (1991) for personality traits with five identified indicators such as extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness; Li (2009) for entrepreneurial competencies with six identified indicators such as opportunity competencies, relationship competencies conceptual competencies organizing competencies, strategic competencies, and commitment competencies; and Moreira et al. (2013) for socioemotional needs. Permission to use the questionnaires were obtained from authors by individually writing a letter and sending it through e-mail.

More so, following the validation, pilot testing was carried out. The gathered preliminary data were subjected to an internal consistency type of validity test using Cronbach's alpha and their respective scores were as follows: personality traits (0.959), entrepreneurial competencies (0.980), and socioemotional needs (0.945) which suggested an internal consistency of "Excellent" (Streiner, 2003) or the items are well-aligned and consistent. Similarly, the questionnaires were designed in a comprehensive form with the help of expert validators. Consequently, the overall mean score for the ratings of experts as to the validity of the questionnaire is 4.53 which suggested "Excellent".

Further, all adapted questionnaires utilized a five-point Likert scale of "Very High" with a numerical value of "5" which means that all variables are always evident, followed by "High" with a numerical value of "4" which means that all variables are often evident. Then, it was followed by "Moderate" with a numerical value of "3" which means that all variables are sometimes evident. Afterwards, it was followed by "Low" with a numerical value of "2" which means that all variables are seldom evident and lastly followed by "Very Low" with a numerical value of "1" which means that all variables are not evident.

Procedure

Certain steps and procedures during data collection were followed. First, a letter to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent, Division of Davao Occidental, requesting permission to conduct the study after the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) had approved its questionnaire for survey administration with UMERB Certification number 2023-396 dated October 16, 2023, was made. Second, a permission letter was sent to the principal of each of the public schools in one district in the Division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines authorizing the conduct of the survey. The validated survey questionnaires were administered to respondents after obtaining permission and consent. Clear instructions were provided to ensure accurate data collection, and all responses were statistically processed at an alpha 0.05 significance level. The data analysis was reviewed and interpreted to generate findings and recommendations.

Data Analysis

A variety of statistical tools were used to provide a more detailed analysis and interpretation of the data. Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the level of personality traits, entrepreneurial competencies, and socioemotional needs. Pearson product moment correlation (Pearson r) was used to determine the significance on the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies, between personality traits and socioemotional needs, and between socioemotional needs and entrepreneurial competencies. Regression analysis, particularly Sobel Z-test was used to determine whether the moderating variable has substantially altered the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. In other words, this test would determine the statistical significance of a moderating effect (Abu-Bader & Jones, 2021). This was used to examine the moderating role of socioemotional needs on the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies among TLE teachers in the Schools Division of Davao Occidental.

Ethical Considerations

The study strictly adhered to the assessment points for ethical considerations as provided by the University of Mindanao Ethics and Review Committee (UMERC). For voluntary participation, respondents were given the free will and voluntariness to participate in the study. Before they answered the survey questionnaire, they were informed that they voluntarily participated in the study and their consent was not tainted by force, fear, threat, intimidation, or coercion. Respondents were reassured that they were not put at risk of harm because of their participation. Also, the study followed Data Privacy Act of 2012 for privacy and confidentiality, keeping their responses anonymous and securely stored. Participants gave informed consent, with the freedom to withdraw at any time, and only those meeting the inclusion criteria were selected. All data, both physical and digital, was securely handled and destroyed after the study. Proper citation was assured to avoid plagiarism. Grammarly, Turnitin, and/or any other plagiarism checker ensured that the grammar was consistent, and the degree of similarity was minimized, allowing to put the ideas from several studies into one's own words of preference and choice. No conflict of interest was present, and permission from the relevant organization was obtained. The manuscript was carefully authored, with significant contributions acknowledged, including the thesis adviser since the thesis adviser provided guidance and direction in refining the study.

Results and Discussion

Level of Personality Traits of TLE Teachers

Shown in Table 1 is the assessment on the level of personality traits of the 300 randomly selected public school TLE teachers in three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines. It can be observed that the overall mean was 3.96, standard deviation of 0.51, with a descriptive rating of "high", indicating that TLE public school teachers' personality traits are oftentimes evident. As shown in the same table, agreeableness obtained the highest mean score of 4.32, standard deviation of 0.68 described as "very high", followed by conscientiousness with a mean score of 4.28, standard deviation of 0.50 described as "very high". Extraversion has a mean score of 4.19, standard deviation of 0.70, and openness with a mean score of 3.80, standard deviation of 0.61 described as "high" while neuroticism has the lowest mean score of 3.20, standard deviation of 0.85 described as "moderate".

Table 1. *Level of Personality Traits of TLE Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Extraversion	4.19	0.70	High
Agreeableness	4.32	0.68	Very High
Conscientiousness	4.28	0.50	Very High
Neuroticism	3.20	0.85	Moderate
Openness	3.80	0.61	High
Overall	3.96	0.51	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Very High; 3.40-4.19, High; 2.60-3.39, Moderate; 1.80-2.59, Low; 1.00-1.79, Very Low

The result implied that TLE teachers' personality traits are functional and efficient in strengthening character education which friendliness, ability to serve as a role model, understanding of learning, discipline, respect for students, impartiality in the application of consequences, patience, calmness, and willingness to pursue life goals. This implied that TLE teachers are devoted, enthusiastic, convincing, and involved. They have seen themselves as helpful and unselfish with others, has a forgiving nature, trusting, considerate

and kind, cooperative, reliable, does things efficiently and less on being depressed, worrisome, and get nervous easily. Part of extraversion is being assertive and enthusiast and being open are becoming values artistic and deep thinker in sharing aesthetic experiences.

In this way, personality of a teacher shows up influence of concealed curricula on the methods of instruction (Istiyono et al., 2021). With this, the impact of teachers with high expectations differs from that of teachers with low expectations and anticipations of success (Lavy, 2020). This has been congruent with Suryanto et al., (2023), and Komariah and Nihayah (2023) that these attributes may support the development of a pleasant work environment at the institution and assist in winning over parents' trust.

Level of Entrepreneurial Competencies of TLE Teachers

Shown in Table 2 is the assessment on the level of entrepreneurial competencies of the 300 randomly selected public school TLE teachers in three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines. It can be observed that the overall mean score was 4.19, standard deviation of 0.57 described as “high”, indicating that TLE public school teachers’ entrepreneurial competencies are oftentimes evident. As shown in the same table, strategic competence obtained the highest mean score of 4.37, standard deviation of 0.68, described as “very high”, followed by organizational competence with a mean score of 4.31, standard deviation of 0.71, opportunity competence with a mean score of 4.24, standard deviation of 0.69, and commitment competence with a mean score of 4.20, standard deviation of 0.72 described as “very high” while conceptual competence has a mean score of 4.10, standard deviation of 0.68, human relations competence with a mean score of 4.06, standard deviation of 0.70, and technical competence with a mean score of 4.06, standard deviation of 0.77, described as “low”.

Table 2. *Level of Entrepreneurial Competencies of TLE Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Conceptual Competence	4.10	0.68	High
Human Relations Competence	4.06	0.70	High
Technical Competence	4.06	0.77	High
Commitment Competence	4.20	0.72	Very High
Opportunity Competence	4.24	0.69	Very High
Organizational Competence	4.31	0.71	Very High
Strategic Competence	4.37	0.68	Very High
Overall	4.19	0.57	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Very High; 3.40-4.19, High; 2.60-3.39, Moderate; 1.80-2.59, Low; 1.00-1.79, Very Low

A key component of every entrepreneurial endeavor's success is entrepreneurial competency and business management expertise. Based on results, since strategic, organizational, opportunity and commitment competencies are very evident to TLE teachers, this implied that since TLE teachers are responsible for teaching entrepreneurship, they should also possess these abilities. Without becoming entrepreneurs themselves, teachers cannot teach others how to be entrepreneurs and a multitude of individual and contextual variables contribute to the development in entrepreneurial intention; however, those associated with entrepreneurship education and training are particularly significant.

The result supports the idea that TLE teachers are concerned about meeting their goals, have clear plans, try to think of all the problems they may encounter (Joensuu-Salo et al., 2020; Kuckertz, 2021; San-Martín et al., 2021). This also supports that they deal with problems as they arise rather than spend time to anticipate them (Leffler, 2020), look for things that need to be done, and determine the best way of conducting market analysis to promote and sell products, services, and ideas (Anjum et al., 2021; Mayuga, 2022; Tu & Akhter, 2023). Further, this illustrated that TLE teachers have the knowledge of processes and characteristics that is central to entrepreneurial activities (Verduijn and Berglund, 2020), carry out ongoing activities involving running a business (Barcelona et al., 2023) and can determine the direction of an organization and identify a strategy to achieve that direction (Amoy, 2024).

Level of Socioemotional Needs of TLE Teachers

Table 3. *Level of Socio Emotional Needs of TLE Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Initial Training	3.69	0.63	High
Coping with Students Deficits	2.53	0.72	Low
School/Teachers Need	4.02	0.66	High
Learning/Teaching Process	4.07	0.67	High
Overall	3.57	0.55	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Very High; 3.40-4.19, High; 2.60-3.39, Moderate; 1.80-2.59, Low; 1.00-1.79, Very Low

Shown in Table 3 is the assessment on the level of socioemotional needs of the 300 randomly selected public school TLE teachers in three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines. It can be observed that the overall mean score was 3.57, standard deviation of 0.55, with a descriptive rating of “high”, indicating that TLE public school teachers’ socioemotional needs are oftentimes evident. As shown in the same table, Learning/Teaching Process obtained the highest mean score of 4.07, standard deviation of 0.67 described as “high”, followed by School/Teachers Need with a mean score of 4.02, standard deviation of 0.66, Initial Training with a mean score of 3.69, standard deviation of 0.63, and lowest on coping with students deficits with a mean score of 2.53, standard

deviation of 0.72 described as “low”.

The implication of these results is that TLE teachers in the Division of Davao Occidental experience significant socioemotional needs, especially in areas such as the Learning/Teaching Process and School/Teachers Need, which were rated as high. This suggests that teachers may require additional emotional support and resources related to their teaching roles and interactions within the school environment. The lower score for Coping with Students’ Deficits indicates that teachers may feel less challenged or supported in addressing students’ academic weaknesses, which may need further attention or targeted interventions. Overall, these findings highlight the importance of addressing the socioemotional well-being of teachers to enhance their effectiveness and well-being, which, in turn, could positively impact student outcomes. This suggests that TLE teachers recognize their students’ emotions and have insight into what is causing them.

Furthermore, the result supports the idea that teachers can purposefully educate and improve these abilities by using evidence-based ways to instruct, approach, and promote excellent behavior (Duchesneau, 2020). The establishment of a solid basis for secure and constructive education serves to augment students’ capacity to excel academically (Hill, 2020), professionally, and in their personal lives through socioemotional needs (Ryan, 2021). This can aid teachers respond with compassionate understanding when a student is acting out—and re-direct the students’ behavior appropriately. In socioemotional needs, it provides the foundation for educational success and learning (Gimbert et al., 2023).

Significance on the Relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurship Competencies

Displayed in Table 4 were the results of the test of relationship between the personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies of the 300 randomly selected public school TLE teachers in three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines. Based on the analysis, overall Personality Traits positively and significantly correlated with overall Entrepreneurial Competencies ($r=0.846$, $p<0.05$). Moreover, the indicators of Personality Traits also significantly correlated with Entrepreneurial Competencies: Extraversion ($r=0.884$, $p<0.05$), Agreeableness ($r=0.881$, $p<0.05$), Conscientiousness ($r=0.773$, $p<0.05$), Openness ($r=0.559$, $p<0.05$), and Neuroticism ($r=0.231$, $p<0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. Further, this signifies that there is a significant relationship between the personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies of the 300 randomly selected public school TLE teachers in three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines.

Table 4. *Significance on the Relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Competencies of TLE Teachers*

Personality Traits	Entrepreneurial Competencies							Overall
	COC	HRC	TEC	CMC	OPC	ORC	STC	
Extraversion	.481**	.485**	.378**	.975**	.950**	.870**	.860**	.884**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Agreeableness	.470**	.462**	.338**	.888**	.912**	.981**	.937**	.881**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Conscientiousness	.598**	.628**	.580**	.642**	.622**	.613**	.670**	.773**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Neuroticism	.283**	.334**	.250**	.152**	.123*	.089	.064	.231**
	.000	.000	.000	.008	.033	.126	.269	.000
Openness	.594**	.639**	.476**	.402**	.369**	.347**	.317**	.559**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.616**	.648**	.508**	.783**	.761**	.739**	.720**	.846**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

**Significant at 0.05 significance level.

The implication of this result is that personality traits play a crucial role in shaping the entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers. The strong and significant correlations between overall Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Competencies ($r=0.846$) suggest that teachers with specific personality traits are more likely to possess and develop entrepreneurial skills. Among the individual traits, Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, and Openness showed particularly strong positive correlations, indicating that teachers who are more outgoing, agreeable, organized, and open to new experiences are more likely to exhibit strong entrepreneurial competencies. On the other hand, Neuroticism had a lower correlation, suggesting that high emotional stability is beneficial for entrepreneurial success. This finding reinforces the importance of fostering positive personality traits in teachers to enhance their entrepreneurial capabilities and ultimately improve the quality of entrepreneurship education. The rejection of the null hypothesis supports the view that there is a significant relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies among TLE teachers.

This supported the idea that cognitive, affective, and behavioral patterns of TLE teachers are enduring and consistent (Hernández et al., 2021), but vary across individuals (Chien-Chi et al., 2020) and this has affected how the specific knowledge, skills, and abilities required for TLE teachers when it comes to entrepreneurship skills, to proficiently initiate, oversee, and expand enterprises (Verduijn & Berglund, 2020). More so, teacher’s attitude has a big effect on the way they are acquainted in determining the best way of conducting market analysis to promote and sell products, services, and ideas or the knowledge of processes and characteristics that is central to

entrepreneurial activities (López-Núñez et al., 2020; Bazkiaei et al., 2020). How motivated, disciplined, social, academically successful, and eager to learn teachers with relation to entrepreneurial competence are determined by their personality traits (Tittel & Terzidis 2020).

Significance on the Relationship between Personality Traits and Socioemotional Needs

Displayed in Table 5 were the results of the test of relationship between the personality traits and socioemotional needs of the 300 randomly selected public school TLE teachers in three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines. Based on the analysis, overall Personality Traits positively and significantly correlated with overall Socioemotional Needs ($r=0.856$, $p<0.05$). Moreover, the indicators of Personality Traits also significantly correlated with Socioemotional Needs: Openness ($r=0.935$, $p<0.05$), Neuroticism ($r=0.763$, $p<0.05$), Conscientiousness ($r=0.727$, $p<0.05$), Extraversion ($r=0.452$, $p<0.05$), and Agreeableness ($r=0.392$, $p<0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. This signifies that there is a significant relationship between the personality traits and socioemotional needs of the 300 randomly selected public school TLE teachers in three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines.

Table 5. Significance on the Relationship between Personality Traits and Socio Emotional Needs of TLE Teachers

Personality Traits	Socio Emotional Needs				
	Initial Training	Coping with Students Deficits	School/ Teachers Need	Learning/ Teaching Process	Overall
Extraversion	.253**	.214**	.543**	.492**	.452**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Agreeableness	.176**	.158**	.500**	.470**	.392**
	.002	.006	.000	.000	.000
Conscientiousness	.655**	.481**	.614**	.664**	.727**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Neuroticism	.910**	.857**	.425**	.321**	.763**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Openness	.728**	.880**	.845**	.625**	.935**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.728**	.697**	.753**	.652**	.856**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

**Significant at 0.05 significance level.

The implication of the result is that personality traits have a significant and positive relationship with the socioemotional needs of TLE teachers. The strong correlation between overall personality traits and socioemotional needs suggests that teachers' personal characteristics, such as openness, neuroticism, conscientiousness, extraversion, and agreeableness, influence the extent to which they experience and fulfill their socioemotional needs. Specifically, the high correlation with Openness and Neuroticism implies that teachers who are more open to new experiences and those who may experience higher levels of emotional stress are more likely to have pronounced socioemotional needs.

This finding underscores the importance of considering personality traits when assessing or supporting the emotional and social well-being of teachers, suggesting that interventions focused on personality development could positively impact teachers' ability to meet their socioemotional needs and improve their overall well-being. Results implied that the ways that TLE teachers think, feel, and act are persistent and maintained but are different for each person and this has impacted self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, responsible decision-making, and interpersonal competency required.

In addition, this has been in support to the idea that their classroom role, teachers act as keen observers, recognizing any obstacles that hinder a child's social and emotional development, such as mental health issues, and collaborating with parents to guarantee access to suitable support systems (Soriano, 2023). This indicates that the level of dedication, enthusiasm, persuasiveness, and engagement shown by TLE teachers has a substantial impact on their demonstration of warmth, caring, and respect. This has facilitated the establishment of reliable relationships (Glickman & Burns, 2020). This further exemplified that the way TLE teachers noted themselves as helpful and selfless, with a forgiving disposition, trusting, considerate and kind, cooperative, reliable, efficient, and less overwhelmed by depression, worry, and anxiety (Komariah & Nihayah, 2023) can influence their ability to be compassionate and understanding towards a student who is exhibiting disruptive behavior, and to redirect the student's conduct appropriately (Paulynice, 2020).

Significance on the Relationship between Socio Emotional Needs and Entrepreneurial Competencies

Displayed in Table 6 were the results of the test of relationship between the socioemotional needs and entrepreneurial competencies of the 300 randomly selected public school TLE teachers in three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines. Based on the analysis, overall Socioemotional Needs positively and significantly correlated with overall Entrepreneurial Competencies ($r=0.667$, $p<0.05$). Moreover, the indicators of Socioemotional Needs also significantly correlated with Entrepreneurial Competencies: Learning/Teaching Process ($r=0.808$, $p<0.05$), School/Teachers Need ($r=0.703$, $p<0.05$), Initial Training ($r=0.370$, $p<0.05$), and Coping with Students Deficits ($r=0.333$, $p<0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected.

Table 6. Significance on the Relationship between Socio Emotional Needs and Entrepreneurial Competencies of TLE Teachers

Socio Emotional Needs	Entrepreneurial Competencies							Overall
	COC	HRC	TEC	CMC	OPC	ORC	STC	
Initial Training	.402**	.463**	.406**	.249**	.218**	.175**	.161**	.370**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.002	.005	.000
Coping with Students	.385**	.453**	.334**	.218**	.177**	.167**	.134*	.333**
Deficits	.000	.000	.000	.000	.002	.004	.021	.000
School/	.730**	.698**	.532**	.533**	.516**	.485**	.468**	.703**
Teachers Need	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Learning/	.868**	.944**	.850**	.475**	.471**	.463**	.461**	.808**
Teaching Process	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.719**	.772**	.639**	.444**	.415**	.388**	.367**	.667**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

**Significant at 0.05 significance level.

The implication of this result is that socioemotional needs have a significant positive relationship with entrepreneurial competencies in TLE teachers. The overall correlation indicates that teachers with higher socioemotional needs are more likely to demonstrate stronger entrepreneurial competencies. Specifically, the strongest correlations with Learning/Teaching Process and School/Teachers Need suggest that teachers' emotional and social needs influence their ability to effectively engage in the teaching process and manage their role within the school environment. Furthermore, the positive correlations with Initial Training and Coping with Students Deficits imply that meeting socioemotional needs may also play a role in teachers' entrepreneurial skills related to professional development and overcoming challenges in the classroom.

This finding highlights the importance of addressing teachers' emotional and social needs to enhance their entrepreneurial competencies, which are crucial for adapting to the dynamic demands of teaching and education (Kesler, 2020). It supported the idea that the expressions of warmth, caring, and respect by TLE teachers contribute to the establishment of a reliable relationship (Posey, 2022). This has a substantial correlation with the understanding of procedures and principles that are essential to the entrepreneurial activities (Basal, 2022; Biadnes, 2022). This factor may influence TLE teachers in their knowledge on the execution of continuing business operations (Ayson et al., 2024), which in turn can shape the future course of an organization and enable the development of a plan to attain the desired goal (Mayuga, 2022).

Moderating Effect of Socioemotional Needs on the Relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Competencies

Table 7 illustrates a Medgraph using Sobel Z-test to prove the moderating effect and to strengthen the obtained result on the significance moderating effect of socioemotional needs on the relationship between the personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies of the 300 randomly selected public school TLE teachers in three districts of the division of Davao Occidental, Region XI, Philippines.

According to the Medgraph utilizing the Sobel z-test presented, the H01 is personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies has an Estimate Value of 1.563, computed standard error of 0.118 and regression coefficient of 13.280 ($p < 0.05^*$), which means the relationship is significant. More so, H02 is socioemotional needs and entrepreneurial competencies has an Estimate Value of 0.243, computed standard error of 0.127 and regression coefficient of 1.909 ($p < 0.05^*$), which means the relationship is not significant. H03 is interaction and entrepreneurial competencies has an Estimate Value of -0.115, computed standard error of 0.028 and regression coefficient of -4.088 ($p < 0.05^*$), which means the relationship is significant.

Table 7. Moderating Effect of Socioemotional Needs on the Relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Competencies

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Entrep Competencies <---	Personality Traits	1.563	.118	13.280	***	H01
Entrep Competencies <---	Interaction	-.115	.028	-4.088	***	Ho3
Entrep Competencies <---	Socio Emotional Needs	.243	.127	1.909	.056	H02

Implications on the results in H01 suggests that TLE teachers indeed possess persistent and consistent patterns of thinking, feeling, and acting, but these patterns fluctuate for each individual. This has changed the specific knowledge, skills, and abilities that TLE teachers need when it comes to entrepreneurship skills, to start, run, and grow enterprises. Teachers' attitudes have a big impact on how well students learn how to do market research to promote and sell goods, services, and ideas, or how well they learn the processes and traits that are essential to being an entrepreneur.

Implications on the results in H03 suggests that since TLE teachers promote entrepreneurship, they should have these skills. Without becoming entrepreneurs, teachers cannot teach others how to be entrepreneurs, and many individual and environmental factors influence entrepreneurial intent. Implications on the results in H03 suggests that although there is a trusting connection between students and teachers when teachers show warmth, care, and respect, there is no direct relation when it comes to TLE socioemotional needs and entrepreneurial competencies.

Since Hypotheses 1 and 3 are significant, and only Hypothesis 2 is not significant, hence, there is a partial moderation effect of socioemotional needs on the relationship between the personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies TLE public school teachers. In partial moderation, it indicates the presence of a substantial association between socioemotional needs as the mediator and the entrepreneurial competencies as dependent variable, as well as a certain direct association between personality traits as the independent and entrepreneurial competencies as dependent variable (Busenbark et al., 2022). It exposes the circumstances under which these relationships are either reinforced or diminished (Igartua & Hayes, 2021).

Figure 2. Moderation Analysis of the Three Variables

Seemingly, a partial moderation effect indicates that socioemotional demands somewhat affect the strength of the association between personality traits and entrepreneurial skills, but do not do so entirely. Socioemotional needs may amplify or diminish the influence of personality traits on entrepreneurial competencies; yet a direct correlation between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies remains intact or still exists. Socioemotional needs do influence the relationship but do not fully explain the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial competencies (Jak & Cheung, 2020; Côté et al., 2021).

Furthermore, personality traits are anticipated to affect the entrepreneurial competencies of TLE teachers, influencing their capacity to innovate, initiate, and manage their responsibilities. TLE teachers need to have entrepreneurial skills to cultivate an entrepreneurial mentality in their students, execute new teaching methodologies, and address obstacles effectively (Barcelona et al., 2023). If a teacher's socioemotional needs are unfulfilled, it may impair their entrepreneurial mentality and the use of entrepreneurial skills, regardless of possessing the requisite personality traits (Amoy, 2024). Conversely, satisfying socioemotional needs could boost the positive impact of certain personality traits on entrepreneurial skills. Teachers with strong personality traits may have entrepreneurial skills; nevertheless, their performance might be influenced positively or negatively by their socioemotional needs.

Conclusions

The study reveals that TLE public school teachers in Davao Occidental possess high levels of personality traits, entrepreneurial competencies, and socioemotional needs. It establishes significant relationships among these three factors, with socioemotional needs partially moderating the influence of personality traits on entrepreneurial competencies. This suggests that while socioemotional needs contribute to how personality traits shape entrepreneurial skills, they do not fully determine the outcome. These findings align with McClelland's Competency Theory, which emphasizes competence as a combination of observable behaviors and underlying characteristics. Enhancing teachers' professional competence and fostering a positive educational environment can improve their personality traits and engagement in entrepreneurial teaching practices.

From a practical perspective, recognizing the role of socioemotional needs can help educational institutions and policymakers develop targeted support systems for teachers. Providing emotional and social support, such as recognition and a conducive work environment, can enhance the effect of personality traits on entrepreneurial competencies. Teacher training programs should integrate both skill development and emotional reinforcement to ensure teachers reach their full potential. Addressing socioemotional needs can further motivate teachers to incorporate entrepreneurial approaches in their teaching, ultimately fostering a more dynamic and effective learning environment that benefits both educators and students.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that educational institutions and policymakers develop targeted programs that enhance the personality traits, entrepreneurial competencies, and socioemotional well-being of TLE public school teachers. Schools should establish support systems that recognize and address the socioemotional needs of teachers, such as mentorship programs, peer support networks, and regular professional development sessions. Providing a conducive and supportive work environment, along with structured recognition and incentives, can help reinforce positive personality traits and improve entrepreneurial competencies. Additionally, policies should be implemented to integrate socioemotional learning into teacher training programs, ensuring that educators receive both technical skills and emotional support to maximize their teaching effectiveness.

Furthermore, teacher training institutions should design competency-based development programs aligned with McClelland's Competency Theory. These programs should focus on identifying and strengthening the key personality traits and entrepreneurial skills necessary for TLE teachers while incorporating strategies to meet their socioemotional needs. Research-driven professional development initiatives should include workshops, leadership training, and experiential learning opportunities that enhance

entrepreneurial teaching practices. Schools should also conduct regular assessments and feedback mechanisms to monitor teachers' progress and ensure continuous improvement. Ultimately, by prioritizing the interplay of personality traits, entrepreneurial competencies, and socioemotional needs, educational stakeholders can create a more dynamic and effective teaching workforce, leading to improved educational outcomes for both teachers and students.

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